

Cryopreservation of Sturgeon Egg Mitochondria and Their Replacement in Germline: A Novel Strategy for Maternal Genetic Preservation in Sturgeons

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Abstract: Nearly all sturgeon species are critically endangered, necessitating to develop innovative approaches to preserve their genetic diversity and support population recovery. Unlike sperm, the cryopreservation of fish eggs or embryos remains technically unscalable. As maternal genetic information is primarily represented by mitochondria, transplanting isolated mitochondria into the vegetal pole of sturgeon embryos, where germ plasm is located and acts as a key precursor for primordial germ cells (PGCs) differentiation, represents a promising conservation strategy. The transplanted mitochondria integrate into the germ plasm and are subsequently incorporated into the germline. Considering seasonality and long generation intervals of sturgeon reproduction, a reliable method for long-term storage of sturgeon egg mitochondria is essential. This study optimized the cryopreservation of sturgeon egg-derived mitochondria, with subsequent validation of mitochondria structural and functional integrity. Various concentrations of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), glycerol, and bovine serum albumin (BSA), combined with different freezing protocols were tested. Functionality was assessed through four key mitochondrial parameters: adenosine triphosphate synthesis, reactive oxygen species production, mitochondrial membrane potential, and integrity. For the first time, we demonstrated that sturgeon egg mitochondria can be successfully cryopreserved, recovered using transplantation and incorporated into the germline. Therefore, we restored maternal germplasm in sturgeon embryos. This work establishes a vital technological advance for conservation biology, offering an alternative approach to preserving and restoring maternal genetic information, which is currently unachievable through other methods in fish.

Keywords: Egg mitochondria, Cryopreservation, Maternal genetic, Mitochondrial transplantation, Sturgeon conservation

Introduction

Sturgeons (Acipenseriformes) are one of the most critically endangered groups of species, necessitating urgent and effective measures to conserve their remaining diversity. However, the development of efficient techniques for cryopreserving fish eggs and embryos has been particularly challenging due to the large size of the oocyte, high yolk content, and low permeability to cryoprotectants [1]. As a result, maternal genetics, represented primarily by mitochondria, cannot currently be successfully preserved. This limitation has driven the exploration of alternative methods to secure matrilineal genetic information.

Sturgeons exhibit a unique mode of germline development that makes them an exceptional model for studying germ plasm and its components independently of other embryonic lineages. In sturgeon embryos, germ plasm is localized exclusively at the vegetal pole, where PGCs are formed, while the remaining vegetal hemisphere is utilized as endogenous nutrition in the form of yolky cells [2–4]. This spatial separation allows for targeted experimental manipulation of germ plasm without affecting other somatic lineages. Building on this unique developmental architecture, we developed a novel method for the elimination of germ plasm including mitochondria using UV irradiation [5]. In turn we transplanted exogenous mitochondria specifically into the germplasm and they rescued PGCs formation. Transplantation of egg-derived mitochondria fully restored the function of the germ plasm and enabled the development of primordial germ cells (PGCs). These mitochondria were subsequently incorporated into the germline [6]. These findings highlight the necessity of optimizing cryopreservation methods to ensure the availability of healthy, functional mitochondria for such conservation techniques.

While mitochondria have been isolated and cryopreserved since the 1970s, using cryoprotectants such as glycerol and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) [7], this technology remains underdeveloped, with varying degrees of success depending on the species and protocol used [8]. Cryopreservation, freezing, and thawing processes often disrupt mitochondrial structural and functional integrity, limiting their usability in research and applications [9–12]. To date, no studies on the cryopreservation of isolated sturgeon egg mitochondria have been identified, underscoring the necessity for optimized methodologies in this context.

In parallel, alternative approaches have sought to address the challenges of cryopreserving fish eggs and embryos by focusing on germline stem cells, such as embryonic PGCs or adult gonial stem cells [13,14]. These cells can be isolated from a target species and stored in liquid nitrogen, preserving their functionality for future use. Upon thawing, they can be transplanted into surrogate parents with depleted germ cells to produce donor-derived progeny [15–17]. This biotechnology has shown success in several fish species, including advancements in optimizing gonial stem cell transplantation in interspecies recipients for sturgeon [18]. Methods to eliminate PGCs, such as antisense morpholino oligonucleotides [19], CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing targeting the *dnd1* gene [20], and UV irradiation targeting the germ plasm [5], have

further refined these techniques. However, despite significant progress, achieving full surrogate reproduction in sturgeons has yet to be achieved [21–23].

The present study aimed to preserve isolated sturgeon egg mitochondria for extended periods without compromising their structural and functional integrity. Furthermore, we sought to evaluate their capacity for transplantation and their ability to rescue PGCs. Mitochondria were isolated from fresh ovulated eggs, cryopreserved using various concentrations of DMSO and glycerol, supplemented with bovine serum albumin (BSA), and subjected to different freezing rates. After one week of cryopreservation, the mitochondria were thawed at 37 °C, and their functional status were reassessed. We found that mitochondria cryopreserved using 15% DMSO containing 1% BSA and the slow freezing method, which involves placing cryovials containing mitochondria and cryomedium into a deep freezer set to –80 °C, exhibited the highest functional performance. Additionally, mitochondria cryopreserved using this method retained their transplantation capacity and were functional in rescuing PGCs even after one year of storage. These findings represent a significant step toward developing reliable methods for preserving maternal genetic information in endangered sturgeons and provide an alternative approach for addressing the broader challenges of germline preservation and surrogate reproduction in fish species.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethics

All experimental procedures were performed in accordance with National and Institutional guidelines on animal experimentation and care and were approved by the Animal Research Committee of the Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia in Ceske Budejovice (FFPW USB).

Experimental design

The experimental design is shown in Figure 1, detailing four consecutive experiments. Trial 1 focused on identifying the optimal freezing method by isolating mitochondria from freshly ovulated sturgeon eggs and evaluating their functional performance under both fresh and cryopreserved conditions using different freezing methods. Trial 2 explored the protective efficiency of various concentrations of cryoprotectants, with particular attention to DMSO and glycerol. Based on the outcome, trial 3 investigated the impact of supplementing cryopreservation media with BSA for enhanced protection. The functional performance of mitochondria across all three trials was analyzed through between-group comparisons after one week of cryopreservation, along with comparisons to fresh mitochondria. Finally, mitochondria cryopreserved using the selected procedure were tested in a transplantation assay to compare their ability to restore germplasm function and PGCs development with freshly isolated mitochondria.

Fig 1. Schematic of study design. The figure was created with BioRender.

Sturgeon egg mitochondria preparation and pre-cryopreservation analysis

Crude mitochondria were isolated by double centrifugation using Mitochondria Isolation Kit (Cat# MITOISO1, SIGMA-ALDRICH®) according to the manufacture's protocol. Briefly, fresh eggs sample (50-100 mg) were homogenized with 10 volumes of extraction buffer (100 mM MOPS, pH 7.5, containing 550 mM KCl and 5 mM EGTA) containing 2 mg/ml albumin (Cat# A0474, SIGMA-ALDRICH®). The homogenate was centrifuged at $600 \times g$ for 5 min at 4°C . The resulting supernatant was collected and centrifuged at $11,000 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C . The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was resuspended in 10 volumes of extraction buffer. This two-step differential centrifugation process was repeated. The final mitochondrial pellet was resuspended in storage buffer (50 mM HEPES, pH 7.5, containing 1.25 M sucrose, 5 mM ATP, 0.4 mM ADP, 25 mM sodium succinate, 10 mM K_2HPO_4 , and 5 mM DTT) at 40 mL per 100 mg tissue.

The crude mitochondrial suspension was further purified using Percoll density gradient centrifugation following a previously established protocol [7] with modifications. Fresh stocks of 40% and 24% Percoll (Cat# P1644, SIGMA-ALDRICH®) were prepared in storage buffer. An equal volume of 24% Percoll was added to the mitochondrial suspension to achieve a final Percoll concentration of 12%. Sequentially, 3.5 ml of 40% Percoll, 24% Percoll, and 12% Percoll containing mitochondria were carefully layered in 12 ml ultra-clear tubes. The tubes were centrifuged in a swinging bucket rotor (SW 32 Ti) at $30,700 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C in an Optima L-90K ultracentrifuge (Beckman Coulter). A yellowish turbid band formed at the interface of the

40% and 24% layers. This band was carefully collected and transferred to fresh tubes. The tubes were then filled with a storage buffer and centrifuged at $16,700 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C . After centrifugation, the supernatant was removed, and the pellet was resuspended in a fresh storage buffer. A final centrifugation step was performed at $11,000 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C . The resulting mitochondrial pellet was resuspended in storage buffer for subsequent use. The protein concentration of the purified mitochondria was determined using a BCA protein assay kit (Cat# 23225, ThermoFisher SCIENTIFIC).

After completing isolation and purification, mitochondrial integrity, adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis and Reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation content, and membrane potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$) analysis with fresh mitochondrial suspension were immediately performed.

Cryopreservation of mitochondria

In cryopreservation experiments, we added various concentrations (0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25%, 30%, 35%, 40%, 45%, 50%, v/v) of both DMSO and glycerol to the egg mitochondria suspension combining with different concentrations (0%, 1%, 2%, 3%, 4%, 5%, 6%) of BSA in 1.8ml cryotubes. Three repeats for each group. The samples were mixed and then immediately frozen with different freezing methods. These include either storing the samples directly into a -80°C deep freezer with a validated temperature control system to ensure consistent and reliable storage conditions, submerging them in liquid nitrogen, or placing the samples in CoolCell[®] FTS30 Cell Freezing Container (Azenta Life Sciences) and cooling them to -80°C at a uniform freezing rate of $\sim 1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ followed by transfer and storage in liquid nitrogen.

Recovery of mitochondria

For further analysis, the cryotube was thawed in a circulating water bath at 37°C to reanimate mitochondria. Once the cryopreservation medium was completely thawed, the tube was centrifuged at $600 \times g$ for 5 min at 4°C . The resulting supernatant was carefully transferred and centrifuged at $11,000 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C to remove the cryomedium. Then the supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was resuspended in storage buffer, washed once more and finally stored in storage buffer at 4°C until use.

Mitochondrial Staining

Mitochondrial staining using the MitoTracker Green dye (Cat# M7514, SIGMA-ALDRICH[®]) was performed to assess the mitochondrial abundance and integrity. MitoTracker Green binds covalently to mitochondrial proteins independently of membrane potential, serving as a specific and reliable marker of mitochondrial structure. The dye was dissolved in DMSO to prepare a 1 mM stock solution. A working solution of 200 nM was prepared by diluting the stock solution in storage buffer immediately before use. The mitochondrial suspension was centrifuged at $11,000 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C to obtain a pellet, which was gently resuspended in prewarmed (37°C) staining solution containing the MitoTracker probe. The suspension was incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature. After incubation, the suspension was centrifuged again to re-pellet the

mitochondria, and the pellet was resuspended in storage buffer. The stained mitochondria were then observed and quantified using fluorescence microscopy (Olympus fluorescence microscope) to evaluate their abundance.

Measurement of ATP synthesis content

The mitochondrial ATP content was measured by CellTiter-Glo® Luminescent Cell Viability Assay kit (Cat# G7570, Promega) according to Rahi et al. [24] with modifications. Briefly, 10^{-1} to 10^{-5} mM concentrations of ATP standards were first prepared in storage buffer. Then 100 μ L of standards, blank (storage buffer) and fresh or frozen 10-fold diluted sturgeon egg mitochondrial suspension were added to the Nunclon 96 Flat Bottom White Polystyrene plate (ThermoFisher SCIENTIFIC) and mixed with 100 μ L of CellTiter-Glo® Reagent in 3 replicates. The plate was put into a luminometer (Tecan Infinite® 200), and the measurement procedure was according to the protocol's recommendation of 2 min shaking followed by 10 min of incubation at 25 °C. The results were obtained in arbitrary light units that were interpolated on the ATP standard curve. Finally, the ATP content in each treatment was calculated and expressed in nmol.

Measurement of ROS generation concentration

Mitochondrial ROS concentration was measured using DCF ROS/RNS Assay Kit (Ab238535, Abcam) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Hydrogen Peroxide (H_2O_2) standards were first prepared in Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) with concentration ranging from 0 μ M to 20 μ M. Subsequently, 50 μ L of standards, blank and 100-fold diluted samples were added to the microplate wells and mixed with 50 μ L of Catalyst for fluorescence measurement, in triplicate. The plate was incubated for 5 min at room temperature, followed by the addition of 100 μ L of DCFH solution to each well. The plate was then covered and incubated at room temperature for an additional 30 min. The fluorescence was read with the luminometer (Tecan Infinite® 200) at 480 nm excitation and 530 nm emission. The results were obtained in arbitrary light units that were interpolated on the H_2O_2 standard curve. Finally, the ROS concentration was calculated and expressed as μ M H_2O_2 per μ g protein.

Membrane potential assay

Mitochondrial membrane potential was measured by the cationic carbocyanine dye JC-1 (Cat# J4519, SIGMA-ALDRICH®) according to the manufacture's protocol. For the control tube, 1.9 ml $1 \times$ JC-1 Assay Buffer, 100 μ L Storage Buffer and 2 μ L JC-1 stain were sequentially added. For the sample tube, 1.9 ml JC-1 Assay Buffer, 100 μ L Storage Buffer, 10 μ L fresh or frozen mitochondrial suspension were added, followed by the addition of 2 μ L JC-1 stain to start the reaction. Each group was prepared in triplicate. The tubes were immediately mixed by inversion and incubated in dark at room temperature for 7 min to allow complete uptake of the dye into mitochondria. Subsequently, 200 μ L from each group were added to the wells of a BioLite 96 well plate (ThermoFisher SCIENTIFIC) and the fluorescence was read in a spectrofluorometer (Tecan Infinite® 200) at 490 nm excitation and 590 nm emission. The fluorescence produced in the

sample was calculated and expressed in per mg of mitochondrial protein (FLU/mgP).

Transplantation of mitochondria into germ plasm of embryos

In the present study, we used gametes from sterlet (*Acipenser ruthenus*). The collection and preparation of gametes, as well as the injection of mitochondria, were performed according to the protocol outlined in previous study [6]. Briefly, after fertilization, the embryos from three different females were dechorionated. Two-thirds of the dechorionated embryos were placed on a UV transilluminator (TFS 26V, UVP, Analytik Jena), and their vegetal hemispheres were irradiated with 254nm wavelengths for 2min with total doze of 360 mJ/cm² [5]. Subsequently, the embryos were placed on an agar-coated (1 %) dish filled with dechlorinated tap water. The injection experiments were conducted as follows. First, to confirm germ plasm destruction, vegetal pole of irradiated and intact (control) embryos were injected with 2 % FITC-dextran (Cat# FD500S, SIGMA-ALDRICH®, MW=500,000) in 0.2 M potassium chloride (Cat# 16200-31000, PENTA) according to Saito et al. [25], who demonstrated that injecting FITC-dextran into the vegetal pole specifically labels PGCs. Second, to compare the ability of egg mitochondria to rescue PGCs, freshly isolated and cryopreserved Siberian sturgeon (*Acipenser baerii*) egg mitochondria were mixed with 2 % FITC-dextran and microinjected into the vegetal pole of 1-to 4-cell stage UV-irradiated fertilized embryos. The embryos were then incubated at 16 °C in dechlorinated tap water, with water changing twice a day. The number of PGCs visualized by FITC-dextran was assessed under fluorescent microscope (M205FA, Leica Biosystems) at late neurula stage (Note: Each group consisted of 3 females, with a minimum of 100 embryos per female).

Identification of transplanted mitochondria

DNA was extracted from 5 days post hatch (dph) sterlet and Siberian larvae, and from 5dph sterlet larvae injected with mitochondria of Siberian sturgeons using a AllPrep DNA/RNA Mini Kit (Cat# 80004, Qiagen). PCR amplification was then performed using mtDNA specific primers [26]. The amplification conditions were 95 °C for 2 min; 35 cycles of 92 °C for 20 s, 57 °C for 30 s, and 72 °C for 30 s, and last synthesis at 72 °C for 10 min. The PCR product was checked for positive amplification on 2 % agarose gel.

Statistical analysis

The number of PGCs in embryos and the mitochondrial measurement in each treatment group were compared using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons or Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's multiple comparisons. For mitochondrial functional performance measurements, at least three independent mitochondrial samples were prepared for each assay, with each measurement repeated at least three times. *P*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were performed with GraphPad. Prism. 9.5.1.

Results

1. Methodological Overview: Assessment of Mitochondrial Health and Functionality

To comprehensively evaluate mitochondrial health, various key indicators of mitochondrial function were assessed to compare frozen-thawed mitochondria with freshly prepared mitochondria. Loss of mitochondrial membrane potential is a critical event during apoptosis, marking a key step in the cascade of genetic and biochemical processes that lead to programmed cell death [27]. ATP synthesis is a reliable means of assessing oxidative phosphorylation defects, as it directly reflects the primary energy-producing pathway [28], and changes in its levels can affect cellular function. ROS are mainly produced in mitochondria, and mitochondrial dysfunction can result in the excessive formation of ROS [29], contributing to cellular damage [30]. Membrane integrity of mitochondria was also assessed using MitoTracker Green, which stains mitochondria independently of membrane potential by binding to mitochondrial proteins. These assays comprehensively evaluated the quantity, health, and functionality of frozen-thawed mitochondria compared to fresh mitochondria. All measurements were performed immediately after mitochondrial isolation and cryopreservation.

2. The $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ method optimally preserves sturgeon egg mitochondria during cryopreservation

To identify the most effective freezing approach for maintaining mitochondrial integrity after frozen-thawed, we compared different cryopreservation techniques. These include rapid freezing of samples by direct immersion in liquid nitrogen, direct storage in a $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ deep freezer, as well as the use of cell freezing container for a slower freezing to $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a uniform rate of approximately $-1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and then transfer and store in liquid nitrogen. Mitochondrial function was evaluated after one week of cryopreservation with these methods and compared to freshly isolated mitochondria based on $\Delta\Psi_M$, ATP production, ROS levels and mitochondrial integrity.

The functional performance of fresh mitochondria was superior to those of cryopreserved mitochondria across all four groups (Fig 2). We observed that fresh mitochondria exhibited significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher ATP production, $\Delta\Psi_M$, and integrity (Fig 2A, C and D), along with lower ROS concentration (Fig 2B), compared to mitochondria frozen directly in liquid nitrogen or using the uniform rate freezing methods. In contrast, mitochondria stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ freezer showed no significant differences from fresh mitochondria across all four parameters.

Among the cryopreservation methods tested, the $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ freezing method demonstrated the best, which showed significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher ATP production, $\Delta\Psi_M$ and mitochondria integrity compared to the other two approaches. Although there were no statistically significant differences in the generation of ROS, the average values were lower in $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ freezer when compared with liquid nitrogen and the uniform rate of approximately $-1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ methods. Therefore, cryopreservation of mitochondria with a $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ freezer was chosen for subsequent experiments.

Figure. 2 Mitochondrial ATP production, ROS generation, membrane potential and integrity of isolated sturgeon egg mitochondria in fresh and frozen-thawed groups with different freezing methods. A. Mitochondrial ATP production (nM). B. Mitochondrial ROS generation ($\mu\text{M H}_2\text{O}_2$ per μg protein). C. Mitochondrial membrane potential (Fluorescence per mg protein). D. Comparison of mitochondrial membrane integrity using MitoTracker Green staining. Means with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$ by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons).

3. A 15% DMSO concentration is most effective for sturgeon egg mitochondrial cryopreservation

Then various concentrations of DMSO and glycerol were tested as cryoprotectant to determine the optimal conditions for preservation of mitochondrial function. We evaluated concentrations ranging from 0% to 50% (v/v) in groups at 5% intervals, resulting in a total of 11 groups for each cryomedium. Figure 3 presents data on mitochondrial functional performance after freezing with DMSO and glycerol. Compared to fresh mitochondria, frozen-thawed sample (both cryomedium) exhibited reduced $\Delta\Psi_M$, ATP, integrity and higher ROS levels. Our results also demonstrate the essential role of cryoprotectants in maintaining mitochondrial structure and function during the freeze-thaw process.

The findings indicate that DMSO was more effective than glycerol in preserving mitochondrial function. The best preservation was observed at concentrations of 15% DMSO and 20% glycerol (Fig. 3). For mitochondria preserved with 15% DMSO (Table 1), the estimated percentage losses in ATP production, $\Delta\Psi_M$ and integrity were 15.22%, 4.04%, and 15.46%, respectively, compared to fresh mitochondria. In contrast, mitochondria preserved with 20% glycerol exhibited higher overall losses (Table 1), with corresponding values of 39.06%, 13.73%, and 17.88%, respectively. Additionally, the generation of ROS in mitochondria preserved with DMSO and glycerol was approximately 1.69 and 1.78 times higher, respectively, than in fresh mitochondria.

Indeed, in the DMSO cryoprotectant group, the optimal concentration of 15% yielded the best functional outcomes across all analysed parameters after freezing. Specifically, ATP production, and integrity were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher (Fig. 3A and D), and ROS concentration were lower compared to those observed at other concentration groups (Fig. 3B). Regarding $\Delta\Psi_M$, the bioenergetic was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than in the remaining groups, except 10-30% concentration range, which did not show significant differences (Fig. 3C). In the glycerol group, at the optimal concentration of 20%, both ATP and $\Delta\Psi_M$ production revealed significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher compared to other concentration groups after freezing (Fig. 3A' and C'). ROS generation

was significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than in all other concentration groups, except for the 25% concentration group (Fig. 3B'). However, mitochondrial integrity did not exhibit significant differences in any of the concentration groups except the 0% concentration group (Fig. 3D').

In both cryoprotectant groups, mitochondrial functional performance displayed a trend of initially increasing and then decreasing with rising concentration. Within the DMSO group, performance increased from 0 to 15% and then decreased at concentrations higher than 15%. Similarly, in the glycerol group, functionality followed a similar pattern, peaking at a concentration of 20% glycerol before declining at higher concentrations.

Figure 3 Mitochondrial ATP production, ROS generation, membrane potential and integrity of isolated sturgeon egg mitochondria in fresh and frozen-thawed groups with varying concentrations of DMSO and glycerol. A, A'. Mitochondrial ATP production (nM). B, B'. Mitochondrial ROS generation ($\mu\text{M H}_2\text{O}_2$ per μg protein). C, C'. Mitochondrial membrane potential (Fluorescence per mg protein). D, D'. Comparison of mitochondrial membrane integrity using MitoTracker Green staining. Means with different letters are significantly different ($P < 0.05$ by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons or Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's multiple comparisons).

Table 1. Percentage change in mitochondrial ATP, ROS, membrane potential and integrity in different concentrations of DMSO and glycerol groups compared to fresh mitochondria.

Concentration (%)	0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50	
DMSO	ATP	-97.72	-65.32	-31.56	-15.22	-30.73	-42.36	-52.97	-61.16	-72.18	-78.31	-85.36
	ROS	+185.14	+158.26	+122.88	+69.50	+129.51	+139.38	+146.35	+171.70	+176.47	+189.40	+203.69
	$\Delta\Psi\text{M}$	-74.32	-31.94	-18.93	-4.04	-18.29	-16.86	-21.47	-36.29	-41.33	-70.96	-73.66
	Integrity	-90.33	-72.40	-34.93	-15.46	-36.92	-48.09	-56.18	-65.20	-70.11	-66.56	-70.46
Glycerol	ATP	-99.23	-89.06	-68.22	-55.23	-39.06	-56.67	-69.75	-77.89	-83.38	-89.50	-92.55
	ROS	+189.40	+143.63	+134.61	+117.09	+77.96	+112.33	+123.39	+153.50	+174.94	+192.97	+202.50
	$\Delta\Psi\text{M}$	-84.74	-60.80	-49.87	-36.36	-13.73	-32.81	-42.65	-54.72	-52.94	-60.52	-81.25
	Integrity	-92.51	-71.33	-44.79	-38.27	-17.88	-34.02	-35.76	-56.60	-65.73	-66.11	-72.49

"-" indicates lost mitochondrial functional performance, "+" indicates increased mitochondrial functional performance.

4. 1% BSA in 15% DMSO had the highest functional performance in cryopreserved sturgeon egg mitochondria

To optimize mitochondrial cryopreservation and minimize the toxic effects of DMSO, we additionally added BSA concentrations ranging from 1% to 6% in combination with 15% DMSO.

Among the treated groups, 1% BSA consistently improved all measured parameters, while higher concentrations led to declines in performance. Specifically, ATP levels were markedly higher ($p < 0.05$) in the 1% BSA group than in other concentrations (Fig. 4A). ROS generation was significantly lower, and $\Delta\Psi_M$ was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the 1% BSA group compared to all other groups, except for the 2% and 3% BSA groups (Fig. 4B and C). Additionally, only the 2% BSA groups exhibited no significant difference in the mitochondria integrity in all concentration groups compared to the 1% BSA group (Fig. 4D).

Figure. 4 Mitochondrial ATP production, ROS generation, membrane potential and integrity of isolated sturgeon egg mitochondria in fresh and frozen-thawed groups with various concentrations of BSA. A. Mitochondrial ATP production (nM). B. Mitochondrial ROS generation ($\mu\text{M H}_2\text{O}_2$ per μg protein). C. Mitochondrial membrane potential (Fluorescence per mg protein). D. Comparison of mitochondrial membrane integrity using MitoTracker Green staining. Cross lines in all violin plots represent median values, and different letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$ by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's multiple comparisons or Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's multiple comparisons).

5. Mitochondria cryopreserved with 15% DMSO, 1% BSA, at -80°C retained their ability to rescue PGCs as well as fresh mitochondria after thawing

To verify the *in vivo* functionality of mitochondria cryopreserved using the 15% DMSO containing 1% BSA and the -80°C freezing method, we injected the frozen-thawed egg mitochondria from Siberian sturgeon into the vegetal pole of sterlet embryos that had undergone UV irradiation, which lacked endogenous germplasm. And our results indicate that cryopreservation did not disrupt mitochondrial function, they were well retained in functional bioenergy and the capacity to rescue the primordial germ cells of sturgeon.

Compared to the control group, the UV-irradiated group exhibited a significant ($p < 0.05$) reduction in PGCs numbers (Fig. 5A, B and F). In contrast, the injection of both freshly isolated mitochondria and cryopreserved mitochondria led to the recovery of PGCs with no significant differences observed among these two groups and the control group (Fig. 5C, D and F).

Next, we injected mitochondria that had been cryopreserved for one year into embryos and found that their ability to restore PGCs (Fig. 5E) was not different from fresh mitochondria (Fig. 5F). And whether the injected mitochondria were cryopreserved for a week or cryopreserved for a year, they could be identified at the larval stage (Fig. 5G) using sterlet mtDNA specific primers: 5' - TATACACCATTATCTCTATGT - 3' and 5' - GGGAATAACCGTTAATTTGG - 3', and Siberian mtDNA specific primers: 5' - TGTCTGTCTAGAACATATG - 3' and 5' - CAGATGCCAGTAACAGGCTGA - 3' [26].

This indicates that transplanted mitochondria can be successfully incorporated into the germline. Moreover, previous studies have demonstrated that the injected mitochondria can be traced not only in larval PGCs with the fluorescent PKH26 tracer but also identified in individual PGC of larvae using species-specific mtDNA and mtRNA primers [6]. These findings confirmed that isolated sturgeon egg mitochondria can be preserved for a long period of time using 15% DMSO containing 1% BSA and -80 °C. Furthermore, this approach effectively maintains the functional integrity of mitochondria throughout the preservation and thawing process.

Figure 5. Frozen-thawed mitochondria can successfully rescue PGCs formation in germ plasm depleted embryos. A. Control embryo at the 256-cell stage. Box plots: area with FITC-dextran labelled PGCs. B. UV-irradiated embryo. C. UV-irradiated and fresh eggs mitochondria-injected embryo. D. UV-irradiated and one-week cryopreserved eggs mitochondria-injected embryo. E. UV-irradiated and one-year cryopreserved eggs mitochondria-injected embryo. F. Comparison of PGCs numbers in different treatment groups. Control: Control embryo. UV: UV-irradiated embryo. UV+FM: UV-irradiated and fresh eggs mitochondria-injected embryo. UV+1W-CM: UV-irradiated and one-week cryopreserved eggs mitochondria-injected embryo. UV+1Y-CM: UV-irradiated and one-year cryopreserved eggs mitochondria-injected embryo. $N = 113, 107, 88, 43$ and 47 embryos. Cross lines in all box plots represent median values, and different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$ by Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn's multiple comparisons). G. The gel image of species specific PCR (7-9, 16-18) confirming the presence of injected mitochondrial mtDNA in transplanted larvae after PGCs rescue. Samples 1-9: Amplification using Siberian sturgeon mtDNA specific primers. 1-3 are sterlet larvae, showing no

PCR amplification. 4-6 are Siberian sturgeon larvae, exhibiting positive amplification. 7-9 are sterlet embryos after UV irradiation transplanted by Siberian sturgeon mitochondria, showing positive amplification. Samples 10-18: Amplification using sterlet mtDNA specific primers. 10-12 are sterlet larvae, showing positive amplification. 13-15 are Siberian sturgeon larvae, showing no PCR amplification. 16-18 are sterlet embryos after UV irradiation transplanted with Siberian sturgeon mitochondria, showing no PCR amplification. The product length for sterlet and Siberian sturgeon are 190 bp and 138bp, respectively, loaded on 2 % agarose gel. L: 500bp DNA marker.

Discussion

The present study represents a significant advancement in the cryopreservation of sturgeon egg mitochondria, addressing a critical need in fish conservation. Transplanted mitochondria successfully restored PGCs development. Building on our recent work demonstrating that egg mitochondria are indispensable yet replaceable components of germ plasm [6], this study establishes a practical methodology for their long-term storage and functional recovery. By overcoming the technical challenges of preserving maternal genetics in fish eggs and embryos, this approach provides a vital tool for conserving endangered species. Our findings demonstrated that mitochondria cryopreserved using 15% DMSO and 1% BSA, in combination with the -80°C freezing method, retained functionality comparable to freshly isolated mitochondria. This included key parameters such as ATP synthesis, mitochondrial membrane potential, mitochondrial membrane integrity, and ROS production, further confirming their functionality through the restoration of PGCs formation.

Mitochondria for transplantation must originate from fish eggs to function correctly. This presents both an advantage and a challenge. On the one hand, obtaining mitochondria from eggs is relatively straightforward, as egg mitochondria are abundant and accessible. On the other hand, this process requires mature females, which may be a limiting factor in conservation programs, particularly for species with delayed sexual maturity or declining wild populations. Future research should explore alternative approaches, such as the potential use of immature oocytes or in vitro systems, to broaden the applicability of this technology.

Few studies have addressed mitochondrial cryopreservation, particularly in fish, and none have focused on egg mitochondria. Consequently, comparisons must often draw on studies involving other tissues and species. DMSO and glycerol are commonly used cryoprotectants, with DMSO being widely favored due to its rapid penetration, low viscosity, and well-characterized properties [7,31,32]. However, inappropriate concentrations can damage mitochondria, as tolerance varies by species and tissue type. Consistent with previous findings [7,33,34], we observed optimal preservation at 15% DMSO, which significantly maintained mitochondrial functional integrity, including ATP production, ROS regulation, and membrane stability.

DMSO toxicity remains a concern at higher concentrations, but its negative effects can be mitigated by complementary agents such as BSA. A 1% BSA concentration, commonly used in mitochondrial cryopreservation [11,35,36], enhanced the cryoprotective effect while reducing

DMSO-induced toxicity. Our findings align with these studies, further validating the efficacy of this combination.

Cooling rates are also critical for mitochondrial cryopreservation. Excessively fast or slow cooling can damage cells, including mitochondria. Studies have employed a range of methods, from direct freezing in liquid nitrogen to gradual cooling to specific temperatures [8,11,23,37,38]. Our comparison of three commonly used methods revealed that direct freezing at -80°C proved to be a practical method for cryopreserving mitochondria. In this approach, mitochondria in cryovials were placed directly into a freezer, providing effective preservation of sturgeon egg mitochondria despite the lack of controlled cooling rates. This method yielded the best results in terms of mitochondrial integrity and functionality.

Notably, mitochondria cryopreserved for one year retained their ability to rescue PGCs, demonstrating the long-term viability of our approach. This underscores the feasibility of using cryopreserved mitochondria for both conservation and research purposes.

The novel approach described in this study offers a valuable addition to existing reproductive technologies for endangered fish species. Unlike androgenesis [39] or somatic cell nuclear transfer [40,41], which primarily focus on paternal genetics, mitochondrial transplantation uniquely preserves maternal lineages, complementing these methods. Our findings suggest that integrating mitochondrial transplantation with advanced reproductive techniques, such as androgenesis or nuclear transfer, could further enhance the precision and efficacy of conservation efforts.

While our results establish the feasibility of mitochondrial cryopreservation and transplantation, several limitations must be addressed. First, the long-term effects of interspecies mitochondrial transplantation on reproductive success remain unclear. Future studies should examine potential fitness trade-offs and mitochondrial-nuclear interactions over multiple generations. Additionally, our findings open new avenues for exploring the use of mitochondria in resolving germline defects or enhancing fertility in aquaculture species.

In conclusion, this study represents a critical step forward in conservation biology, offering a practical solution for preserving maternal genetic information in sturgeons and potentially other endangered species. By extending the previous foundational findings [6], we demonstrate the feasibility of long-term mitochondrial cryopreservation and its application in restoring germline functionality. This not only enhances the toolkit available for conservation efforts but also provides a robust model for exploring broader questions in germline biology, evolutionary genetics, and reproductive biotechnology.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M.P.: Review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. R.F.: Review & editing, Data curation. L.G.:

Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Table 1. Percentage change in mitochondrial ATP, ROS, membrane potential and integrity in different concentrations of DMSO and glycerol groups compared to fresh mitochondria.

Concentration (%)		0	5	10	15	20	25	30	35	40	45	50
DMSO	ATP	-97.72	-65.32	-31.56	-15.22	-30.73	-42.36	-52.97	-61.16	-72.18	-78.31	-85.36
	ROS	+185.14	+158.26	+122.88	+69.50	+129.51	+139.38	+146.35	+171.70	+176.47	+189.40	+203.69
	$\Delta\Psi$	-74.32	-31.94	-18.93	-4.04	-18.29	-16.86	-21.47	-36.29	-41.33	-70.96	-73.66
	Integrity	-90.33	-72.40	-34.93	-15.46	-36.92	-48.09	-56.18	-65.20	-70.11	-66.56	-70.46
Glycerol	ATP	-99.23	-89.06	-68.22	-55.23	-39.06	-56.67	-69.75	-77.89	-83.38	-89.50	-92.55
	ROS	+189.40	+143.63	+134.61	+117.09	+77.96	+112.33	+123.39	+153.50	+174.94	+192.97	+202.50
	$\Delta\Psi$	-84.74	-60.80	-49.87	-36.36	-13.73	-32.81	-42.65	-54.72	-52.94	-60.52	-81.25
	Integrity	-92.51	-71.33	-44.79	-38.27	-17.88	-34.02	-35.76	-56.60	-65.73	-66.11	-72.49

“-” indicates lost mitochondrial functional performance, “+” indicates increased mitochondrial functional performance.